

Chandra Shumser: the Mimic Man

(An Explorative Study from Postcolonial Perspective)

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Abstract

(The research article explores the mimicry of western especially British values and lifestyle by the Nepalese Rana rulers especially by Chandra Shumser, the fifth Primeminister of Rana autocratic regime of Nepal. Nepalese ruling Rana family was deeply influenced by the white skin colonial authorities and their sophisticated lifestyles. British colonization in the Indian sub continents during 18th and 19th century has propound impact in politics, economics, culture and other aspects of local people. This article explores those impacts on Nepalese Rulers and how the mimicry of western values and lifestyles by the ruling Ranas and their families led to hybridity and mockery lacking their idealism and other traits.)

Introduction:

Though Nepal was not formally colonized by the British, it was not free from its imperial impact and influence. Not only the British authorities dominated but also used Nepalese rulers for their vested interests. On the other hand, the Nepalese rulers struggled for their identity and recognition from the imperial power. They not only allied with the British to maintain their family autocratic rule in Nepal but also imitated and mimicked the western lifestyle for elevating themselves in the eyes of their subjugated common people in Nepal and among the people outside it. If one closely observes Anglo-Nepalese relations during Indian colonization, he can clearly see both active aggression against and passive acceptance of the British imperial power. During unification era Nepal observed policy of isolation with the British authority and after the treaty of Sugauli in 1816 policy of assimilation and acceptance was carried out by the Nepalese rulers especially by the ruling Ranas. Though the Rana rulers tried their best to exclude Western socio-cultural impacts on their subjects, they themselves not only accepted the influence of British but also joined together to manage and strengthen mutual ruling interests. This study focuses on why and how they were motivated in some cases compelled to copy the alien white culture and lifestyle to assume, pretend and show themselves powerful in front of Nepalese people.

In the light of post-colonial study this paper explores the influence of British colonialism in India on Nepalese identity and how it affected the social, political and psychological aspects of the rulers in Nepal. The study focuses on how the Nepalese rulers became helpless in front of the Imperial power and accepted the dominating authority. How they struggled for creating artificial identity and starved for imperial medals, awards and recognition. How their mimicry of the Western values and lifestyle made them hybrid. How the overlapping of foreign culture on their own made them ridiculous. How they felt their own social customs and values inferior and pretended to be more civilized and powerful with foreign culture and Western dress.

Colonization not only motivated but also compelled the local authorities and local people to accept its influence, values and lifestyles leading to hybridity in every aspect of colonized people. This research finally explores and analyzes the political and cultural events and activities during the reign of Chandra Shumsher using the historical-analytical and mixed methods.

1. Life and Contribution of Chandra Shumsher:

Chandra Shumsher was the 5th Rana Prime Minister after Jang Bahadur Rana the 1st Rana Prime Minister who set the Rana familial autocratic rule in Nepal. Chandra Shumsher became the Prime Minister after deposing his brother Dev Shumsher and ruled almost for 28 years from 1901 to till his death in 1929. His dress, lifestyle, interests all were the rough imitation of British authority. He had visited Britain and was honored with many British military titles like GCB (Knight Grand Cross of the Order of the Bath) and GCSI (Knight Grand Commander of the Order of the Star of India) by the British Crown. The most important contribution of Chandra Shumsher is that he became successful in signing the Anglo-Nepalese treaty of 1923 that acknowledged the independent and sovereign status of Nepal in the world. He is known for his several social reforms like abolishing “Sati System” and “Slavery System”, and establishment of educational institutions like Trichandra College. He served as the British ally and participated in the World War-I and strengthened the British recruitment policy in Nepal. He is known for introducing western architecture style in Nepal that after visiting the palace of Versailles, in the influence of British architecture, he built the Singha Durbar (palace) which is now being used as the central administrative centre of Nepalese government. Modernization of Nepalese military power with the modern weapons and the western dress had taken place during his rule.

2. Statement of the Problem:

Though there has been lot of study carried out on Anglo-Nepal relations during the Indian colonization, little or almost no importance has been given in academic field to western mimicry and generated cultural hybridity out of the socio-cultural overlapping during Rana regime in Nepal.

Rana rulers that they mimicked the western lifestyle but not the western liberal ideologies. There is the research gap that nobody has paid interest on how the western mimicry and artificiality of Rana rulers resulted in cultural hybridity and public mockery. To fulfill this gap the researcher has tried to explore and interpret the impacts of British Imperialism on Nepalese Rana Rulers especially on Chandra Shumsher in light of postcolonial perspective. This study focuses on how the mimicry of the Western values and lifestyle made Chandra Shumsher hybrid and how the hybridity and cultural overlapping created confusion that he ran after British military medals, identity and recognition from the Imperial Power.

3. Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the study are as follows:

To explore and interpret the impacts of British imperial policy on Nepalese rulers especially on Chandra Shumsher during rana autocratic regime.

To point out the mimicry of western values and sophisticated lifestyle by the ruling Rana family.

To interpret how the overlapping of the align culture on sacred Nepali culture resulted in cultural hybridity and public mockery.

To trace how the Nepalese rulers (especially Chandra Shumsher) became victim of inferiority complex and helpless in front of Imperial power and accepted the dominating authority for their own identity and stability.

4. Literature Review:

There are so many studies and researches that discuss on the Anglo-Nepalese relations. Little attention has been paid to the impact and response part of British imperialism. And the issue of mimicry of western values and resulting hybridity out of overlapping of alien cultural practices has not been studied yet.

Upreti (2011) discusses on how the British constructed the masculinity of Gurkh soldiers and compares those constructions with the constructed masculinities of two Rana Prime Ministers, Jang Bahadur Rana and Chandra Shumsher.

Liechty (1997) focuses on cultural economy of foreignness and relates its place in the construction of individual, class, and state power in Nepal. He further explores how the persons, ideas, and goods from beyond its borders mean to people in the Kathmandu valley? How were they used, controlled, resisted, or sought after?

Schaefer (2007) focuses especially on impacts and responses of colonial India. He explains that both white men and the Indians were influenced by one another and further assesses that the Britishers abolished certain indigenous customs like Sati System that did not fit to their moral code and simply changed certain customs like Durbar Ceremony that they needed to assume power and ruling legacy and indianized their British Raj.

Cowan (2020) details about the medals and honors like British military titles like GCB, GCSI, KCVO etc that the Nepalese Rana rulers received from the British Crown and compares the weight of those honorary titles within the Rana rulers. He further outlines Nepalese Rana rulers' passion for the honorary titles and awards as the gift of the British sovereign on the one hand and the British policy of awarding certain honorary titles to safeguard its imperial interests on the other.

5. Research Methodology :

Historical-analytical approach has been employed using both the primary and the secondary sources like official decrees and British and Nepali correspondence along with books, journal articles and related historical analysis.

Mixed research has been used in extensive study on the available literature and references available.

The Postcolonial perspective has been used to explore and interpret the issues of imperial domination, struggle for identity, mimicry, cultural overlapping and resulting hybridity etc.

6. Discussion:

As this article focuses on the impacts of British imperialism on Nepalese Rana rulers (especially on Chandra Shumsher) and their responses from the postcolonial perspective, the themes of mimicry, identity, resistance, cultural conflicts and hybridity and so on have been explored. And it examines how

the rulers were portrayed as stereotypes and their culture as inferior or need to be corrected or at least reformed along with the power dynamics between the British imperial power and the Nepalese Rana rulers. This article focuses especially on Chandra Shumsher that he was not only the ally of the British Imperial power but also perfect mimicker of the western lifestyle and their policies. History is evident that Nepal was never formally colonized either by the Mughals or by the British Imperial power, but it was not free from the imperial or colonial impacts. Regarding the influence and impact of the British Imperial power in the contemporary Nepalese politics. Crews (2006) writes “Although Nepal was never formally colonized; its history is nonetheless deeply entangled with the colonial histories and politics of South Asia.” (p. 1).

If one closely observes and analyzes the impacts of and responses to the British Indian colonization especially in Nepal, he can see both aggression against and acceptance of the western values. If he divides Modern Nepali history from the starting of the unification of Prithivinarayan Shas to the end of Rana autocratic regime into two phases from 1723 to 1846 and from 1846 to 1950, he can observe resistance against and acceptance of the western influence and values respectively. King Prithivinarayan Shaha and his successors upto Sugauli treaty of 1816 employed policy of exclusion and isolation with the Imperial Power. Especially the British Imperial power and its practices were seen with awe and skepticism during unification era. The Nepalese rulers not only excluded the western cultural practices but also expelled the Christian capuchin missionaries from Kathmandu valley raising the issues against religious conversion and cultural expansion. Regarding the policy of exclusion, expulsion and aggression Upreti (1992) points out that the policy of isolation was first used by Prithivinarayan Shaha as a tool of foreign policy.

As the first phase of Nepalese modern history from Prithivinarayan Shaha to the signing of Sugauli treaty Nepal responded with aggression and tried to avoid or exclude the Imperial influence within its territory, Anglo-Nepalese relations not only got conflicted but also busted somewhere with violent bloodshed war. Prithivinarayan Shaha as an anti-imperialist responded with Gurilla war near Sindhuligadhi to the captain Kinloch Mission which was marching towards Kathmandu valley to assist the king of Bhaktapur against the Gurkhalis. As the first mission of British Imperial Power to the Himalayan kingdom was bitterly defeated by the Gorkhals in 1767, it took almost 5 decades to the British to prepare for the next military mission against Nepal. And both Nepal and British India not only continued but also competed parallel to expand their territories. Nepal in the name of internal unification in the Mountainous region and British India in the south Asian plains for its Imperial expansion continued to expand their influences. Regarding the parallel activities of expansion of Nepal

and British India Dhungel and Pun (2009) write that the expansion of the Gorkhas in the hills was running parallel to that of the British in the northern and eastern parts.

As both of them were in parallel competition to expand their territories, they got conflicted and confronted in many boarder areas regarding their influence and taxation. Due course Anglo-Nepalese war took place from 1814 to 1816 and ended with the treaty of Sugauli that this defeat not only put full stop to Nepalese part to its unification activities but also Nepal lost its one third territory.

This defeat and loss of territory generated internal conflicts in Nepal. The conflict was not within Durbar but also around Durbar or between and among the Ruling elites especially between the Thapas and the Pandeys. They started to blame each other and this division caused conflict in Palace as well. During this turmoil of internal conflicts between and among ruling families and external influence of British India, Junga Bahadur Rana killed own maternal uncle General Mathabarsingh Thapa and not only took over ruling power but also became successful to establish century long Rana familial autocratic rule in Nepal.

With the rise of Rana autocratic rule, the policy of isolation and exclusion got ended and the Rana rulers accepted the British authority and its imperial influence. So far as the matter of the British imperial impacts in Nepalese politics during the Rana rule and their dependence on align power for ruling security within is concerned Dhungel and Pun (2009) argue that the Rana political elite relied heavily on British imperial support for their oppressive rule in Nepal.

The Rana rulers not only depended on the British India for maintaining their oppressive rule but also mimicked western values and lifestyle. They started to learn English, teach western education to their children, wore western dress and applied white puff and power. The Rana rulers were not only mimicking the western lifestyle but they were also coping western architecture to erect their palaces and statues. Regarding the mimicry of Rana Rulers and Nepali cultural angst Malla (1979) describes the Rana palaces as "monumental day-dreams of mimicry—each a monstrous monument to the idea of mimicry". For him, Rana cultural practice was simply "a cheap transplantation of the West" being all the more contemptible for amounting to "mimicry of a culture only imperfectly understood." Regarding the cheap transplantation of the west he ridicules:

The first thing they apparently succeeded in accomplishing was a cheap transplantation of the West. By the twilight hours of the Rana regime the architects of the dynasty had succeeded in erecting monumental day-dreams of mimicry—each a monstrous monument to the idea of mimicry. Today each Rana mansion stands as a museum without character. All their walls are covered with sinister life-size portraits of the Rana ancestors, standing either by a dead tiger or a dimpled wife.....They also built a large number of edifices with rhetorical Gothic colonnades or pseudo Greco-Roman motifs, like the Gaddi Baithak,

Military Hospital, Bir Hospital, Trichandra College, Durbar High School; to these were later added glib structures like Saraswati Sadan and the Police Station. (Malla, K. P., 1979, p. 5).

This type of mimicry and wholesale copy of align culture not only conflicted with the local culture but also generated hybridity leading to mockery. Liechty (1997) describes about the cultural conflicts generated by introduction of the align culture and Nepalese response to the white skin foreigners “Europeans—as non-Hindu, beef-eating foreigners encountered serious moral barriers to entering the sacred realm of the Kathmandu valley, South Asian travelers, either Nepalis, Tibetans, or Indians, did not face the same kind of restrictions”. (p.14).

Cultural conflicts and leading hybridity introduced hybrid culture which not only became ridiculous but also subject of mockery. Malla (1979) further ridicules the imported cultural impacts and generated hybridity and confusion by sudden exposure to the western and colonized Indian culture in Kathmandu. Ridiculing the impacts on contemporary youth of Kathmandu, he writes:

In a sense, Kathmandu is metaphysically steeped in Hindu lore. The city priests and patricians are spiritually enchanted by the higher mythology of the Vedas, the Upanishads, the Puranas, the Gita and the epics; the plebians are mentally addicted to the lower mythology of the appetizing Hindi filmdom. In this cinfused anatomy of Kathmandu’s Hindu cociety run arteries of alien blood which provoke the prodigal Hindu youth to dress tighter and tighter, wear shorter and shorter skirt, dance to wilder and wilder beats of the brass, and drink more and more exotic cocktails. The transistor carrying, picnic-minded, twist-obsessed, Hollywood-sinister gangs of Kathmandu’s youth eat a crazy salad in expensive restaurants and every midnight fly past the dark allies of Kathmandu at a record speed. (Malla, K. P., 1979, p. 11).

Among the Rana rulers, Chandra Shumser, the second most influential Rana Primeminister was perfect mimicker of the western values and lifestyle. He introduced western military uniform and training to his troops. He used to dress himself with the British clothes to project himself before both as an ally to the British authority and Modern ruler in front of his own subjects. Regarding the western dress of Chandra Shumser, Upreti (2011) portraits:

by dressing in British clothes and military uniforms, Chandra was not only able to project himself before the English as a modern ally of the Empire, but also succeeded in presenting a model of masculinity that was closer to the prototype of rational, middle-class English masculinity, a masculinity that was different from the physical, impulsive masculinity of its young adults and working-class subjects. (Upteri, S., 2011, p. 34). Not only Chandra Shumser but also whole ruling Rana family and their elites used to use foreign

goods and imported comforts. With the imported European products Rana elites used to expose their superficiality. Litchty (1987) ridicules the Rana mimicry and superficiality as:

To explore these questions I focus on that particular constellation of European products that seem to have been most popular in nineteenth century Kathmandu. These include window glass, chandeliers, clothing (cloth and styles) lanterns and candle reflectors, mirrors ("looking glasses"), telescopes, and portraits. All of these items have in common their involvement in acts of seeing, looking, being seen, and being able to see (sometimes without being seen). They have to do with vision, appearance, and surfaces. (Litchty, M., 1987, p. 64).

They were as much habituated to use imported western consumer goods that to keep well-supplied Chandra Shumsher had institutionalized certain supply chains and buying agencies as Litchty (1987) states:

In order to keep themselves well-supplied with imported "comforts" the Rana regime instituted a variety of new means for acquiring foreign consumer goods, including the aerial ropeway that, by the late 1920s, was able to deliver up to eight tons of freight per hour, "without in any way opening up for passenger traffic the new avenue into the capital" To keep his ropeway busy Chandra established a "foreign goods department attached to the Jinsi Adda" in Kathmandu, and a "buying agency" in Calcutta, that imported European goods for "certain of the Prime Minister's domestic requirements. (Upadhyaya 1992:128, 253). (Litchty, M., 1987, p 51).

The mimicry and wholesale copy of imperial culture generated confusion and hybridity within the Rana family. This type of confusion and hybridity one could observe during the daily activities of Chandra Shumsher that he used to use both European soap and sacred Ganges water during his bath. As Landon (1928) states:

He goes to his first bathe of obligation where soap is used that is of ceremonial purity. After being anointed by purified pastes, he enters a new bath into which a few spoonfuls of the sacred Ganges water have been poured. He then goes to the room set aside for his spiritual observances and there makes his daily symbolic offering to the Brahmans of five rupees and eight annas...(Landon, P.,1928, p.93).

His idea of argument on abolition of slavery supported from both Vedic and western Christian discourses is another perfect example of hybridity and conceptual confusion created by the contact and overlapping of two different cultures coming contact together. As Litchty (1987) further describes about the prose tract document of Chandra Shumsher as follows:

It also made him appear a much more reliable ally of the Empire, one who could be counted on to support British India in its hour of need. No other text points to the rational modernity of Chandra Shumsher more than his famous 'Appeal for the Emancipation of Slaves and Abolition of Slavery', a prose tract that was produced in both Nepali and English. It is an extraordinary document in which Chandra Shumsher draws from both Hindu Vedic sources as well as the discourse of western civilisation to support his argument. (Litchty, M., 1987, p 35).

Regarding the hybrid personality of Chandra Shumsher, Upreti (2011) depicts the description of Chandra Shumsher's image by Landon (1928) as "as an enlightened ruler who, though an upholder of tradition, was simultaneously a modern rational man." (p. 36). Not only does Landon present Chandra Shumsher as a rational, masculine native Kshatriya ruler, but also shows him as "fusing two different models of mastery and masculinity by wearing royal Nepali clothes as well as turning out in English attire". (p.36). He describes the elements of cultural overlapping in Rana elite dress that one could see combination of and compromise between the local and the European traditions. One can observe the western educational impacts as well on Chandra Shumsher that he not only established Durbar High School and Trichandra College for western education to Rana elite family but also visited Oxford during the commemoration week and received the honorary degree of Doctor of Civil Law from the chancellor of the university.

Chandra Shumsher not only mimicked European dress and lifestyle he also introduced the western architect as well. Singha Durbar which was built by Chandra Shumsher after his Europe visit was the perfect example of mimicry. After visiting the Palace of Versailles during his Europe visit, in influence of European architect he built this enormous building which had more than 1000 rooms. Chandra Shumsher's mimicry was not confined within the structure of the building that he mimicked the entire decoration as well. Sharma (1978) describes:

The great Singha Durbar, modeled after Versailles, had a reception hall so fabulous that "there [was] not a hall in all India of such magnificence." Between its towering French windows were "enormous mirrors," statues and paintings. Its ceiling supported tiers of huge crystal chandeliers above an inlaid parquet floor (Landon 1928i:189). The main building alone had more than 1,000 rooms and was said to be the largest structure in all of South and South East Asia. (Sharma, P.R., 1975, p.120).

Chandra Shumser was as much starved for identity and recognition from the Imperial power that his passion for European mimicry lead him to collect the British military titles like GCB (Knight Grand Cross of the Order of the Bath) and GCSI (Knight Grand Commander of the Order of the Star of India) by the British Crown. He valued more the British Military titles than Nepalese national interests that to get honored GCSI he not only facilitated British India to capture Lasha but also compromised of trade route to the Tibet through Kathmandu that British India could use direct trade route to Tibet after Younghusband military mission of 1904. In regard to the direct trade root to Tibet, Shaha (1996) includes:

Chandra Shumsher played in facilitating the Younghusband military mission that crossed the Sikkim-Tibet border and captured first Gyantse and later Lhasa in August 1904. This led to the signing of the Lhasa Convention on 9 September, 1904, and opened up a direct trade route between British India and Tibet through Kalimpong, diminishing 'the volume of trade that passed through Kathmandu by the Kuti and Kerung passes'. Thus, while Chandra Shumsher's help to the British obtained for him the title of Grand Commander of the Star of India, it actually harmed Nepal's trade interests in the long run. (Shaha R., 1996, p. 42.).

Another example of compromise on national interests to get honored and get British awards and titles was that Rana rulers especially Maharaja Chandra Shumser further strengthened and freely allowed Britain to recruit Nepalese youth to British army in return of tenuous and titles. Litchty (1987) argues with Chene (1991) who protraits that how the British imperial policy toward Nepal shifted from material to muscles:

Nineteenth century British policy toward Nepal shifted from one which viewed the country in terms of trade (as a source of Nepali goods, a market for European products, and a route to markets in Tibet), to one which saw Nepal as the source of an important 'raw material'—in this case "native soldiers." In a sense, the Rana government allowed Britain to consume one of Nepal's few natural resources— people—in return for its (often tenuous) sovereignty. (Litchty, M., 1987, p 9). Lord Chelmsford, the viceroy of India, thus offered an annual present of 1 million rupees to Chandra Shumsher, who was also promoted to the post of full general in the British Army in 1919 and was awarded the Grand Cross of the Order of St. Michael and St. George.

Maharaja Chandra Shumser was not simply the mimicker of western lifestyle but the imitator of imperial models as well that he had categorized his own Rana clans into four classes and removed C class category

from role of succession. His mimicry of British model to strengthen own ruling power was with double imperative that he discouraged the Gurkha soldiers and other common subjects to mimic the Englishness while he himself was perfect and role model mimicker. As Upreti (2011) mentions :

Chandra Shumsher's attitude towards Nepali soldiers in the British Army is representative of a strategic double standard: while he strengthened his own cultural power by miming British models, he discouraged a similar imitation of Englishness by common Gurkha soldiers, whom he saw as a possible threat to rule by his family. (Upreti, S. 2011, p. 32).

His belief of "every Englishman is a gentleman" (Landon, P. 1928, ii::2, p.6) is the climax and best example of his mimicry and chivalry that lead him to the position of glorifying the Imperial power in India.

Chandra Shamsher seemed to be fully convinced that the prosperity of Nepal is bound up with the maintenance of British predominance in India, and he was determined that there will be no threat from British power on his autocratic rule in Nepal. As Landon reports his views toward the British authority in India that "the sahib who is no sahib shall never enter Nepal, and weaken my people's belief that every Englishman is a gentleman. - Rana Prime Minister Chandra Shamsher to Percival Landon, mid 1920s (Landon, P. 1928 ii::2, p.6).

Chandra Shumser was not only the mimicker of British modality but also the Imperial Masculinity as well. He used to assert his Imperial masculinity with British uniforms and English manners. To prove and project himself as perfect alloy of the imperial model and masculinity in front of both the Imperial authority and the Nepali subjects he used to arrange the hunting trips with the British Nobility. Landon (1928) describes about the shooting ceremony organized by Rana Prime Ministers to prove their chivalry to the British authority in following words:

Through the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries the Kathmandu government practiced a kind of 'Big Game Diplomacy' through their policy of regularly inviting English nobility to Nepal for elaborate and lavish "shooting expeditions." In the nineteenth century several Princes of Wales came shooting in Nepal and in 1911 came King George V himself, the Emperor of India, following his Imperial Durbar. (Landon, P., 1928, ii:77 pp.130-135).

7. Results:

Maharaja Chandra Shumser Visited Europe and returned with many honorary British military titles and blueprint of western values. In influence he introduced western education, architect and certain social reforms in Nepal. He worked as an ally to the British Imperial power that he not only allowed the British to recruit Nepalese youth in British army but also involved in First World War from British side. He modernized military power in British model with western uniform and training. He became successful to sign the treaty of 1923 with the British which acknowledged the independent status of Nepal in international arena. Among the Rana rulers he was the second most influential after Jang Bahadur Rana and perfect mimicker of Western especially British Imperial values and lifestyle.

8. Conclusion

Chandra Shumser was the mimic man. One can not only observe the impacts of the British Imperial values and western lifestyle on Chandra Shumser but also his submissive responses to those impacts during his rule. His sophisticated lifestyle, his hybrid manners, his western modeled social reforms, introduction of western education and western architect all are the perfect examples of western Mimicry. Close and minute observation of his lifestyle and daily activities displays the cultural overlapping which is leading hybridity and confusion in his life.

9. References :

- 1.Crews, C. (2006). *What about postcolonial politics in Nepal?:* New School for Social Research
- 2.Crowan, S. (2020). *Ranas and gongs:* Kathmandu
- 3.Davis, C. C., (2019). *Theatre of Nepal and the people who make It.* New Delhi: Cambridge University Press.
- 4.Chene, M. D., (1991). *Relics of empire: A cultural history of the gurkhas, 1815-1987.* Ph.D. dissertation, Stanford University.
- 5.Forbes, D. (1962). *The heart of Nepal.* London: Robert Hale Ltd.
- 6.Giuseppe, F. (1790). *An account of the kingdom of Nepal.* Asiaticke Researches
- 7.Joel, M. (1990). *British India's relations with the kingdom of Nepal 1857-1947: A diplomatic history of Nepal.* London: Allen and Unwin.

- 8.Landon, P. (1928). *Nepal. 2 vols.* London: Constable.
- 9.Liechty, M. (1997). *Selective exclusion: Foreigners, foreign goods, and foreignness in modern Nepali history.*
- 10.Malla, K. P. (1979). *Kathmandu your kathmandu: Kathmandu*
- 11.Oliphant, L. (1852). *A journey to Katmandu, the capitol of Nepaul.* London: John Murray
- 12.Onta, P. (1996). *Creating a brave Nepali nation in British India: The Rhetoric of Jati Improvement, Rediscovery of Bhanubhakta and the Writing of Bir History.* Studies in Nepali History and Society 1(1): 37-76.
- 13.Schaefer, C. (2007). *European imperialism and colonial response.* Center for Research Libraries
- 14.Shaha, R. (1996). *Modern Nepal : A political history, 1769-1885, VI.* New Delhi: Manohar Books.
- 15.Sharma, G. N. (1990). *The impact of education during the rana period in Nepal.* Himalayan Research Bulletin
- 16.Sharma, P. R. (1975). *Descriptions of individual monuments in kathmandu valley: The Preservation of Physical Environment and Cultural Heritage, A Protective Inventory, Vol. II.* HMG Dept. of Housing, Building and Physical Planning. Vienna: Anton Schroll & Co.
- 17.Stiller Ludwig F. S. J. (1993). *Nepal: Growth of a nation.* Kathmandu: Human Resources Development Research Center.
- 18.Upadhyaya, S. P. (1992). *Indo-Nepal trade relations: A historical analysis of Nepal's trade with the British India.* Nirala Publication.
- 19.Upreti, S. (2011). *Masculinity and mimicry: ranas and gurkhas : Baha Occasional Papers 5*
- 20.Whelpton, J. (1983). *Jang Bahadur in europe: The first Nepalese mission to the west.* Kathmandu: Sahayogi Press.

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